

Attitude of Health Professionals and Care of Elderly in Nupeland, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examined attitude of health professionals and care of elderly in Nupeland. The descriptive research design of the survey type was used in this study. The population consisted of all health professionals and elderly people above 65 years old in Nupeland. The sample size for this study consisted of 294 health professionals and 581 elderly people above 65 years old from Nupe tribe in Nupeland. The sample was selected using multi stage sampling procedure. Two sets of questionnaire designed by the researcher tagged "Attitude towards Care of the Elderly Questionnaire (ACEQ)" and "Care Received by Elderly Questionnaire (CREQ)" were used to collect relevant data for the study. The validity of the instruments was ensured through face and content validity. The reliability of the instruments (ACEQ and CREQ) was determined by finding the internal consistency which yielded a coefficient value of 0.89 and 0.75 for ACEQ and CREQ respectively. The data collected from the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that health professionals exhibited positive attitude towards the care of the elderly. It was further revealed that there was no significant difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their educational status, religion and gender. It was recommended that healthcare professionals should improve on their own attitude in all aspects of elderly care.

Keywords: Attitude, Health Professionals, Care, Elderly,

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Introduction

Ageing is both a normal and general process; but growing elderly can be as beautiful as it can be painful. Ageing is a biological, social and psychological course. Because ageing is critically a cultural kind, its sense and importance change both historically and culturally. Age, in almost every culture, is one of the major attributes that determine groupings and role descriptions. How old people are, or the response of other people to them, play a key part in influencing how they feel about themselves and whom they relate with, and what the society expects of them. Societal definition of the elderly differs from society to society. In most societies, elderly serves as a pedestal for explaining cultural and social attributes of man for the creation of some of their natural description of social roles (Iwasaki & Jones, 2008).

As an important component of social life, old age is highly revered in indigenous African communities where it is commemorated as 'the age of wisdom and of teaching'. In Nigeria, the elderly are highly respected as the custodians of inherited wisdom and experience and they are the major decision-makers. Nowadays, however, in our dynamic societies, the accrued knowledge of the elderly is scarcely viewed as the spring of wisdom; it is mostly regarded as something outdated and archaic (Pesic, 2007; Loh, 2006).

Ageing is a sensitive and highly regarded issue and it is a course of becoming older. The aged in Nigeria are highly honoured, respected and often held in high esteem. The elderly constitutes a store of wisdom and experiences. In Nigeria, the stress of care majorly rests on family members irrespective of the provisions in the 1999 Constitution, Section 14 2(b) which states categorically that, "The security and welfare of its people shall be the primary purpose of the government" and in Section 16, sub-section 2(d) promises, "That suitable and adequate shelter and suitable and adequate food, reasonable national minimum living wage, old age care and pensions and unemployment, sick benefits and welfare of the disabled are provided for all citizens." Regrettably, the government seems to have backed out of these promises as most aged are not protected by any social security scheme. The only recipients are those in formal job who have pension remuneration which are insufficient and often hindered due to corruption in the pension scheme (Iwasaki & Jones, 2008).

The researcher observed that the elderly in this society makes up the most vulnerable group; however, the least care and concern are shown by the healthcare workforce, the policy makers, researchers and their own families and relations. They appear to be openly snubbed by the most people especially their own immediate families and close relations. This seems to place an unjust and needless burden on the aged who have held significant positions and made huge contributions to the development and welfare of this country.

In the traditional Nupe society the aged occupies a very significant position in the family, the society and the entire region. He/she is seen as a store of knowledge, wisdom, folkways, record and leadership. There are probably about 4.5million Nupes, principally in Niger, Kwara and Kogi States to the FCT. They are mostly Muslims with a few Christians and followers of African Traditional religion. The researcher observed that there is an increasing need for health professionals to show appropriate attitudes toward the elderly. A high standard of care for the elderly seems to be associated with the positive attitudes of health workers.

The health worker, according to Abdulrahem and Parakoyi (2005) plays key roles in determining and ensuring desirable standards of interventions, acting as a professional in developing core of professional knowledge, expertise and should have ability to convey same to others. They are often the providers of services aimed at health maintenance and disease prevention.

Attitude is a core part of human identity (Doherty, Mitchell & Elisabeth, 2011). Everyday people love, hate, like, dislike, favour, oppose, agree, disagree, argue, persuade and so on. All these are evaluative reactions to an object. Attitudes develop and alter with time. According to Ige and Olowolabi (2010), attitudes are influenced by three components. They are cognitive (beliefs, thoughts, attributes), affective (feelings, emotions) and behavioural information (past events, experiences).

A fundamental link in developing the dimension of attitudes toward caring for the aged as a social indicator is to create the relationships between such attitudes and care for the elderly. These links are complex. It is part of the human condition for health workers to do things which are opposing to their beliefs, and it is also true that health workers sometimes fail to act in harmony with their beliefs. Nevertheless, such deviations of what might be expected are seen as variation, and it appears logical to suppose that on the whole, health workers are more likely to behave in harmony with their beliefs than in disharmony to them (Engstrom & Fagerberg, 2011).

Unfavourable attitudes and stereotypes of elderly people are also believed to stand as a hindrance to the successful care of the elderly people (Lee, Wong, & Loh, 2006). The researcher observed that some people express unconstructive attitude towards old people. When caring for elderly people, some health workers were more likely to use physical constraints, to disrespect their independence and dignity and show favouritism against them (Weiss 2005).

Sadly, standards connected with old age are changing, while young family, health workers' attitude towards the elderly are changing, the effectiveness of the traditional way of caring for the elderly is also being compromise because of the ways old age and the elderly are perceived by young family members. The change in attitude of old age has been attributed by Researchers to the effects of urban, modern and western influence (Liu, Norman & While, 2013).

This study therefore examined attitude of health professionals and care of elderly in Nupeland. The study specifically examined:

- i. the attitude of health professionals towards the care of the elderly in Nupeland;
- ii. the relationship between the attitude of health professionals and care received by the elderly; and
- iii. the difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their educational status, religion and gender.

Research Question

This research question will be raised to guide the study:

1. What is the attitude of health professionals towards the care of the elderly in Nupeland?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between the attitude of health professionals and care received by the elderly in Nupeland
2. There is no significant difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their educational status.
3. There is no significant difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their religion
4. There is no significant difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their gender.

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive research design of the survey type was used in this study. The design was considered appropriate because it focuses on the observations and perception of the existing situation of attitude toward care of the elderly among Nupe people in North Central, Nigeria. This describes and interprets what is concerned with attitude towards care of the elderly without manipulation of variables. The population consisted of all health professionals and elderly people above 65 years old in Nupeland. The sample size for this study consisted of 294 health professionals and 581 elderly people above 65 years old from Nupe tribe in Nupeland. The sample was selected using multi stage sampling procedure.

Two sets of questionnaire designed by the researcher tagged "Attitude towards Care of the Elderly Questionnaire (ACEQ)" and "Care Received by Elderly Questionnaire (CREQ)" were used to collect relevant data for the study. The ACEQ was administered on the health professionals and it consisted of two sections namely Section A and Section B. *Section A* sought for bio-data of the respondents. *Section B* consisted of 15 items to elicit information on attitude towards the caring of the elderly.

The CREQ was administered on the elderly people and it consisted of two sections namely Section A and Section B. *Section A* sought for bio-data of the respondents while *Section B* consisted of 20 items to elicit information on the extent of care received by the elderly people. The instruments adopted 4 point scale of Likert type as follows: Strongly Agree (SA) - 4, Agree (A) - 3, Disagree (D) - 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) - 1.

The validity of the instruments was ensured through face and content validity. The items in the Questionnaire were presented to experts in the fields of Health Education and Tests and Measurement. To ensure face validity of the instrument, the experts helped to determine the facial value of the instrument.

To ensure content validity, the experts including researcher's supervisor checked the items and ascertain that they represented the variables and its adequacy to measure what it was meant for. The experts took time to check the extent to which items of the instruments represented the adequacy and suitability of the items being measured. In so doing, all irrelevances and ambiguous items were eliminated.

The reliability of the instruments (ACEQ and CREQ) was determined by finding the internal consistency through a study carried out among the Nupe people in Ondo and Ekiti States which is outside the sampled locations. The instruments were administered on 20 health professionals and 20 elderly people above 65 years of age. ACEQ was administered on health professionals while CREQ was administered on elderly people. In order to ascertain reliability of the instruments, data collected were tested using Cronbach's alpha to determine the internal consistency of the items which yielded a co-efficient value of 0.89 and 0.75 for ACEQ and CREQ respectively.

The researcher personally administered the instruments with the help of 2 trained research assistants from each of the state sampled in the study. The data collected from the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Hypotheses 1 was tested using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Analysis, hypotheses 2 – 3 were tested using one – way Analysis of Variance while hypothesis 4 was tested using t-test. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the attitude of health professionals towards the care of the elderly in Nupeland?

In answering this question, data on attitude towards care of the elderly in Nupeland were collected from the responses of the respondents to items under Section B of ACEQ (items 1 – 15). The data were collated and analysed using descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation. In table 2, the mean score cut-off mark of 2.50 was derived by finding the average of the scoring system. Mean score of items greater than mean cut-off of 2.50 were accepted while those less than 2.50 were rejected.

Table 1: Mean Scores of attitude of health professionals towards the care of the elderly

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	S.D	Remark
1.	I feel good taking care of the elderly	2.95	0.72	Agreed
2.	I see the care of the elderly people as being time consuming.	1.69	0.46	Disagreed
3.	I prefer giving attention to younger people than the elderly ones	1.86	0.42	Disagreed
4.	Time should not be wasted for elderly persons with terminal illnesses.	1.73	0.45	Disagreed
5.	The older the elderly the more demanding he/she becomes.	2.92	0.76	Agreed
6.	The elderly do not deserve the care health workers give them.	1.76	0.43	Disagreed
7.	Some elderly look untidy and dirty. And as such I do not like caring for them.	1.67	0.53	Disagreed
8.	The majority of the elderly are senile	1.70	0.46	Disagreed
9.	I get stressed up when taking care of the elderly	1.91	0.28	Disagreed
10.	The elderly can often provoke the care giver.	1.68	0.52	Disagreed
11.	I like taking care of older people.	2.55	0.50	Agreed
12.	I neglect myself and concentrate only on the aged when taking care of them.	2.96	0.21	Agreed
13.	Elderly patients exhibit different behaviors which affect their care	2.98	0.17	Agreed
14.	It is difficult to convince reluctant patient about their care in the hospital	2.53	0.50	Agreed
15.	Working with older people does not appeal to me at all	1.41	0.49	Disagreed

Mean Cut-off: 2.50

Table 1 showed the attitude of health professionals towards the care of the elderly. Using the criterion mean score of 2.50 as cut-off to determine the affirmative of each statement, the respondents agreed that they feel good taking care of the elderly, the older the elderly the more demanding he/she becomes, they like taking care of older people; and they concentrate only on the aged when taking care of them. However, most of the respondents disagreed that they see the care of the elderly people as being time consuming; they prefer giving attention to younger people than the elderly ones, among others. From the above table, it can be concluded that the health professionals have positive attitude towards the care of the elderly in Nupeland.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between the attitude of health professionals and care received by the elderly in Nupeland

Table 2: Relationship between the attitude of health professionals and care received by the elderly

Variables	N	Mean	Stand Dev	r-cal	P-value
Attitude towards care of the elderly	294	32.28	2.13	0.675*	0.000
Care received by the elderly	581	53.74	4.69		

*P<0.05

Table 2 showed a positive relationship between the attitude of health professionals and care received by the elderly in Nupeland. The r-calculated value of 0.675 is significant at 0.05 level ($r = 0.675, p < 0.05$). This indicated that there was a significant positive relationship between the attitude of health professionals and care received by the elderly in Nupeland. The null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that attitude towards care of elderly increases is moderately related to the care received by the elderly.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their educational status.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance for difference in attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their educational status

Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.681	2	.840	0.184	.832
Within Groups	1331.887	291	4.577		
Total	1333.568	293			

P > 0.05

The result presented in Table 3 showed that F_{cal} value of 0.184 was not significant because the P value (0.832) > 0.05 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that there was no significant difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their educational status.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their religion

Table 4: Analysis of Variance for difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their religion

Groups	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	18.053	2	9.027	1.997	.138
Within Groups	1315.515	291	4.521		
Total	1333.568	293			

P > 0.05

The result presented in Table 4 showed that F_{cal} value of 1.997 was not significant because the P value (0.138) > 0.05 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that there was no significant difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their religion.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their gender.

Table 5: Difference in attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their gender

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Male	109	32.43	2.14	292	0.918	0.359
Female	185	32.19	2.13			

P>0.05

Table 5 shows that the t-cal value of 0.918 was not significant because the P value (0.359) > 0.05. This implies that null hypothesis was not rejected. Hence, there was no significant difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their gender.

Discussion

Health professionals have positive attitude towards the care of the elderly in Nupeland. In consonance with this finding, Oyetunde, Ojo and Ojewale (2013) found out that health professionals showed positive attitude towards the care of the elderly and good knowledge of ageing process. The submission of Okoye and Asa (2011) however contradicted this finding as they concluded that most of the healthcare professionals have negative attitude towards the care of the elderly as most of them preferred taking care of young adult than elderly people.

The findings further revealed that there was significant relationship between the attitude of health professionals and care received by the elderly in Nupeland. This implies that the attitude of knowledge of health professionals will determine the care received by the elderly people. Ayenibiowo, Kehinde, Obashoro-John and Ayeni (2014) found a significant relationship between the attitude of health professionals and care received by the elderly people. Redmond, Guerin and Devitt (2008) however contradicted this finding as they submitted that ageism has been found to negatively affect the attitude of health care professionals, both implicitly through unfair resource allocation by stakeholders and explicitly by providing offensive and poor quality treatment.

The findings however revealed that there was no significant difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their educational status. The submission of Loh (2006) contradicted the findings of this study as he submitted that registered health professionals with master's degree hold positive attitude towards the care of the elderly while less educated health professionals display the most negative attitude (Loh, 2006).

The study further revealed that there was no significant difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their religion. Almost all religions viewed elderly care as God's blessing and eternal reward. This finding is in consonance with the finding of Jimada (2005) who concluded that religion has no influence on attitude of caregivers towards care of the elderly.

The findings of the study further revealed that there was no significant difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their gender. This implies that both male and female health professionals have almost the same attitude towards care of the elderly. This finding however is not in consonance with the findings of Herdman (2002) and Cicirelli (2003) who concluded that gender influences the attitude of care of the elderly as female health professionals are easily stressed up and have frustrating feeling and a feeling of guilt when their care receivers are not satisfied

Conclusion and Recommendation

It is concluded that health professionals exhibited positive attitude towards the care of the elderly. It is further concluded that there was no difference in the attitude of health professionals towards care of the elderly based on their educational status, religion and gender. It is recommended that healthcare professionals should improve on their own attitude in all aspects of elderly care.

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